

PRINSTON SMART ENGINEERS

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Certificate of Internship

HVAC DESIGN

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future professionals

HAFEEZ BASHEER MOHAMMED

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY

1SU18ME037

Intern Has Successfully Completed The Internship.
Intern Was Found To Be Good And Disciplined.
August 9th to September 13th, 2021.

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PSEHVAC2661

S.K.LASER TECH

No.3408, 8th cross, 2nd Stage Kamakshipalya, Magadi Main Road, Bangalore-79.

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Mr. ABHISHEK.S.**, Register No. **1SU19ME701**, studying in 7th semester in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, **SUCET**, Mangalore has successfully completed his internship at **S.K.LASER TECH** workshop at Kamakshipalya, Bangalore from 28/06/2021 to 30/07/2021.

We found that he is diligent and sincere towards his training during his participation with us.

We wish him all the best for his future endeavor.

Place : Bangalore

Date : 02/08/2021

FROM

S.K.LASER TECH

MFRS. OF: HEAVY INDUSTRIAL FABRICATIONS, PRECISION MACHINED COMPONENTS

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉಪಕರಣಾಗಾರ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ

Govt. Tool Room & Training Centre

Sub Centre

A Govt. of Karnataka Society

Plot No. 7E, Industrial Area, Baikampady,
Mangalore - 575 011, INDIA
Telefax : 0824 - 2408003
Email : gttcmng@gmail.com

GTTC/TRG/IS/HVP/8/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. HRITHWIK V POOJARY . S/O Mr. S VIJAYA KUMAR. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE
Plot No. 7E, Industrial Area,
Baikampady, Mangalore - 575 011

Head Office : Rajajinagar Industrial Estate, Bangalore - 560 010
Phone : 080 - 23152118, 23157189, Fax : 080 - 23301683, Email : gttcb@dataone.in
Website : www.karunadu.gov.in/gttc

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉಪಕರಣಾಗಾರ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ

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Telefax : 0824 - 2408003

Email : gttcmng@gmail.com

GTTC/TRG/IS/RRK/7/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. RAKESH R KULAL . S/O Mr. RAJU KULAL. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRAINING CENTRE
Plot No. 7E, Industrial Area,
Baikampady, Mangalore - 575 011

Head Office : Rajajinagar Industrial Estate, Bangalore - 560 010

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Website : www.karunadu.gov.in/gttc

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Telefax : 0824 - 2408003
Email : gttcmng@gmail.com

GTTC/TRG/IS/RKM/15/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. ROHITHKUMAR M. S/O Mr. MALLESHA N.
of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has
undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic
curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021.
He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the
internship report.

Principal
PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE,
Plot No. 7E, Industrial Area
Baikampady, Mangalore - 575 011

CERTIFICATE
OF COURSE COMPLETION

RANJU H.R

for successfully completing your course in "Auto Cad" from
15 November 2021 to 30 December 2021

03/01/2022

DATE

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "J. H. R.", positioned above the Director's title.

DIRECTOR

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉಪಕರಣಾಗಾರ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ

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13-08-2021

GTTC/TRG/IS/JYK/14/2021-22

This is to certify that Mr. JNANESH Y K . S/O Mr. YOGISH KULAL. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

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GTTC/TRG/IS/SJS/12/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. SANJAY J SHETTY . S/O Mr. JAYANTH SHETTY. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

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GTTC/TRG/IS/A/9/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. ABHISHEK . S/O Mr. BHASKARA. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

(Signature)
Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE,
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GTTC/TRG/IS/SS/16/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. SUNIL S . S/O Mr. SHREEDHARA M A. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE

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Govt. Tool Room & Training Centre

Sub Centre

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Mangalore - 575 011. INDIA

Telefax : 0824 - 2408003

Email : gttcmng@gmail.com

GTTC/TRG/IS/PS/11/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. PRANAM S SALIAN . S/O Mr. SURAJ SALIAN K. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE

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Website : www.karunadu.gov.in/gttc

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GTTC/TRG/IS/UDP/03/2021-22

30-09-2021

This is to certify that Mr. ROYSON D'SILVA S/O Mr. RONALD D'SILVA of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering and Technology Mukka Mangalore, has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 31-08-2021 To 30-09-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

[Handwritten Signature]

Principal

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉಪಕರಣಾಗಾರ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ

Govt. Tool Room & Training Centre

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Telefax : 0824 - 2408003

Email : gttcmng@gmail.com

GTTC/TRG/IS/S/10/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. SHASHANKA . S/O Mr. SHANKAR B SHETTIGAR. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE

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Mangalore - 575 011. INDIA

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Website : www.karunadu.gov.in/gttc

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GTTC/TRG/IS/UDP/01/2021-22

30-09-2021

This is to certify that Mr. **SANNIDHI**. S/O Mr. VITTALA ACHARYA of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering and Technology Mukka Mangalore, has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 31-08-2021 To 30-09-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

S. Sannidhi

Principal

ಸರ್ಕಾರಿ ಉಪಕರಣಾಗಾರ ಮತ್ತು ತರಬೇತಿ ಕೇಂದ್ರ

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GTTC/TRG/IS/NN/6/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. NIKHIL NAYAK . S/O Mr. NITHYANANDA NAYAK. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

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GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CENTRE,
Plot No. 7E, Industrial Area
Baikampady, Mangalore - 575 011

Head Office : Rajajinagar Industrial Estate, Bangalore - 560 010

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CERTIFICATE

Awarded To Mr. ASHWIN S JOHNSON

Of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, MUKKA, MANGALURU

For Participation In The Automotive Mechanical, Electrical & Electronics-

Basic Course From 05-07-2021 TO 31-07-2021 On Maruti Suzuki Range Of Vehicles.

Nerenki Parshwanath
Chief General Manager
(Service & Spares)

Trainee Code: 1530
Date: 31-07-2021

KNOWLEDGE IS POWER

BUT KNOWLEDGE, WITHOUT PRACTICE IS NOTHING

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GTTC/TRG/IS/S/13/2021-22

13-08-2021

This is to certify that Mr. SURAJ . S/O Mr. SUDESH RAIKER K. of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY college of engineering Mangalore has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 05-07-2021 To 04-08-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal
PRINCIPAL / UNIT HEAD
GOVT. TOOL ROOM & TRG CEN

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Website : www.karunadu.gov.in/gttc

GTTC/TRG/IS/UDP/02/2021-22

30-09-2021

This is to certify that Mr. **DINAKARA**. S/O Mr. **GOPAL MOGAVEERA** of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** college of engineering and Technology Mukka Mangalore, has undergone Internship Training at our institution as a part of their academic curriculum. The duration of the training was from 31-08-2021 To 30-09-2021. He has successfully completed the Internship Training & submitted the internship report.

Principal

